

Chronic Kidney Disease of Unknown Etiology: Clinico-Epidemiological study insights from a Hospital-Based Cross-Sectional Study in Western India

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Received: 15-12-2024 / Revised: 20-12-2024 / Accepted: 24-12-2024

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Background: Chronic kidney disease of unknown etiology (CKDu), characterized by the absence of known risk factors, has been documented in various geographically distinct regions worldwide. This study explores the clinical and epidemiological profile of patients with CKDu from a newly identified hotspot in western India.

Materials and Methods: This cross-sectional study analyzed the sociodemographic, clinical, and laboratory profiles of CKDu patients visiting a tertiary care public hospital in, between July 2024 and December 2024. CKDu was defined as progressive CKD with minimal proteinuria, no hematuria, and the absence of diabetes, severe hypertension, systemic illness, glomerulonephritis, or other urinary tract diseases. Symmetrically contracted kidneys on ultrasound further confirmed the diagnosis.

Results: The mean age of patients was 53.6 ± 11.8 years, with a male predominance 68.1%. Most patients were from rural areas (88.6%) and were primarily engaged in farming (63.3%). The average estimated glomerular filtration rate (eGFR) at presentation was 21.5 ± 15.1 mL/min/1.73 m². Patients were categorized as having stage 3 CKD (26.5%), stage 4 CKD (34.3%), or stage 5 CKD (39.2%).

Conclusion: This study identifies distinct geographical clustering of CKDu cases in western part of India, suggesting the need for further investigation into potential environmental or occupational risk factors in these regions.

Keywords: CKD, Etiology and Nephrology.

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Introduction

Chronic kidney disease (CKD) is a significant global public health issue, characterized by a progressive decline in renal function that leads to increased morbidity, reduced quality of life, and premature mortality [1]. Traditionally, CKD has been attributed to well-established risk factors such as diabetes, hypertension, glomerulonephritis, and other systemic illnesses. However, in recent decades, an emerging form of CKD, referred to as chronic kidney disease of unknown etiology (CKDu), has garnered global attention. CKDu is distinct in its occurrence as it manifests in individuals without traditional risk factors, posing a unique challenge to clinicians, researchers, and policymakers alike [2].

The phenomenon of CKDu has been reported in geographically and culturally diverse populations, predominantly from rural and agrarian regions. Areas such as Central America, Sri Lanka, and parts of South Asia have reported clusters of CKDu cases, with affected individuals often being

agricultural workers exposed to environmental toxins, extreme heat, or dehydration. In India, the Uddanam region of Andhra Pradesh was among the first areas where CKDu gained widespread recognition, earning the disease the eponym "Uddanam nephropathy." More recently, CKDu cases have been reported from other regions in India, including western India, where its impact has begun to draw the attention of researchers and public health authorities [3].

The etiology of CKDu remains a subject of ongoing investigation. Hypotheses range from chronic exposure to environmental toxins, heavy metals, agrochemicals, or infectious agents, to factors such as repeated dehydration and genetic predisposition [4, 5]. Despite this, the disease continues to challenge healthcare systems, particularly in rural areas where healthcare access and diagnostic facilities are limited. Understanding the clinico-epidemiological characteristics of CKDu in specific regions is therefore crucial to

identifying potential causative factors, implementing effective interventions, and guiding public health strategies to mitigate the disease's burden [6, 7].

This hospital-based cross-sectional study aims to provide comprehensive insights into the demographic, clinical, and laboratory profiles of CKDu patients in western India. By focusing on a tertiary care center that serves as a referral hub for rural populations, the study highlights the unique characteristics and clustering of CKDu cases in the region. Through this, we aim to contribute to the growing body of knowledge on CKDu, providing a foundation for future research and informing strategies to alleviate the burden of this enigmatic and debilitating condition.

Materials and Methods

The study analyzed data from adult patients presenting with chronic kidney disease (CKD) at the Swaminarayan Institute of Medical Sciences and Research, a tertiary-level hospital located in Kalol, Ahmedabad during the period from July 2024 and December 2024. The study provides a unique opportunity to examine the clinico-epidemiological profile of CKD patients across a diverse and contiguous population in western India. The diagnosis of Chronic Kidney Disease of Unknown Etiology (CKDu) was established in patients presenting with chronic kidney disease (CKD), characterized by at least two estimated glomerular filtration rate (eGFR) values of <60 ml/min/1.73m², measured at least three months apart. These patients exhibited absent or subnephrotic proteinuria and no evidence of hematuria, diabetes, or severe arterial hypertension (defined as blood pressure $<160/100$ mmHg in untreated individuals or $<140/90$ mmHg in those receiving up to two antihypertensive medications).

Furthermore, the diagnosis excluded systemic illnesses, glomerulonephritis, or other urinary tract diseases as potential causes of CKD. Ultrasound imaging was required to confirm symmetrically contracted kidneys. In cases where patients presented with normal-sized kidneys, a kidney biopsy was performed to rule out other underlying pathologies.

Data collection for this study was conducted both retrospectively, following approval from the Institutional Ethics Committee. Sociodemographic, occupational, clinical, and laboratory data were gathered through patient interviews and by extracting relevant information from their medical records. All collected data were systematically recorded in a structured proforma. The estimated glomerular filtration rate (eGFR) was calculated using the Chronic Kidney Disease Epidemiology Collaboration (CKD-EPI) 2009 equation[7], specifically adapted for non-Black populations, to ensure accurate assessment of kidney function.

Results

During the study period, a total of 110 patients were diagnosed with CKD of unknown etiology (CKDu). The mean age of these patients was 53.6 ± 11.8 years, and the majority were male (68.1%). A significant proportion of the patients originated from rural areas (88.6%), highlighting the geographical clustering of CKDu cases. The majority of CKDu cases were from Central Gujarat (n = 49, 44.5%), South Gujarat (n = 37, 33.6%) and North Gujarat (n = 24, 21.8%). These findings underscore the importance of further investigation into the environmental and socioeconomic factors contributing to the high prevalence of CKDu in these districts [Table 1].

Table 1: Distribution and Sociodemographic profile of CKDu patients

Characteristics	n (%)
Central Gujarat	49 (44.5)
South Gujarat	37 (33.6)
North Gujarat	24 (21.8)
Age (years)	53.63±11.76
21–30	10 (9.0)
31–40	17 (15.4)
41–50	27 (24.5)
51–60	42 (38.1)
>60	41 (37.2)
Male	75 (68.1)
Education	
Illiterate	50 (46.4)
Primary/secondary	38 (34.5)
Higher secondary school	12 (13.0)
Graduate and above	10(9.0)
Occupation	
Unemployed	7 (6.0)
Farmer	70 (63.3)

Homemaker	13 (12.0)
Clerk	2 (1.8)
Laborer	13 (12.0)
Shopkeeper	3 (3.0)
Teacher	2 (1.8)
Monthly family income (INR)	
<3000	28 (25.3)
3001–10,000	62 (56.6)
10,001–20,000	11 (10.2)
Don't know	9 (8.1)
Water source	
Hand pump	8 (7.2)
Open water source	15 (13.9)
Tap water	10 (9.0)
Tubewell/borewell	77 (69.9)
Exposed to pesticide, weedicides/fertilizer	59 (53.6)
Personal protective equipment use in agriculture	8 (7.2)
Substance abuse	
Smoking	33 (30.1)
Tobacco	59 (53.0)
Alcohol	18 (16.3)

The majority of the patients in the study were engaged in farming, making up 63.3%. Another 12.0% were involved in unskilled physical labor, while 12.0% were homemakers. A significant concern was the practice among farm workers, with 74.2% of them reporting regular use of fertilizers and pesticides without the use of personal protective equipment (PPE), exposing them to potentially harmful chemicals.

In terms of socio-economic background, a large proportion of the patients came from families with a monthly income below Rs. 10,000, accounting for 81.9% of the participants. This indicates a lower socio-economic status and possibly limited access to healthcare resources and education.

In fact, nearly 50% of the individuals in the study were uneducated, which may impact their awareness of health risks and the importance of protective measures, including the proper handling of agricultural chemicals. Regarding the source of drinking water, the majority of the patients relied on a borewell as their primary water source (69.9%) with a smaller portion depending on an open well (13.9%). This highlights the potential risk of contaminated water sources, which could be a contributing factor to the health conditions of

these individuals, particularly in areas where sanitation and water treatment may be inadequate. These findings suggest that environmental factors, socio-economic status, and lack of education may all play significant roles in the health of the population studied [Table 1]

Table 2 presents the clinical features observed in the patients. The most common symptoms reported included decreased appetite, which was experienced by 42.8% of the patients, weakness in 40.4%, and pedal edema in 39.9%. These symptoms are indicative of underlying health issues that may be related to the patients' working conditions, socio-economic status, or other environmental factors.

Additionally, the table reveals that a significant portion of the patients were using various forms of medication to manage their symptoms. Forty-one point six percent of the patients reported regularly using over-the-counter analgesics, indicating that pain relief was a common self-management approach. Ayurvedic medications were used by 30.7% of the patients, reflecting a reliance on traditional or alternative therapies. A smaller group, comprising 6% used herbal medications, further emphasizing the diversity in the types of treatments sought by the patients.

Table 2: Clinical and laboratory characteristics of CKDu patients

Clinical and laboratory characteristics	n (%)
Symptoms	
Decreased appetite	47 (42.8%)
Weakness	44 (40.4%)
Pedal edema	44 (39.9%)
Vomiting	25 (23.5%)
Joint pain	31 (21.7%)
Back pain	19 (18.1%)

Over-the-counter analgesics use	45 (41.6%)
Ayurvedic medication use	34 (30.7%)
Herbal medication use	7 (6.0%)
BMI (kg/m ²), mean±SD	19.97±3.46
≥18.5	36 (33.1%)
≥18.5–24.9	66 (59.6%)
≥25	8 (7.2%)
Systolic blood pressure (mmHg), mean±SD	121.86±12.97
Diastolic blood pressure (mmHg), mean±SD	76.05±9.78
No. of patients on antihypertensive medications at enrollment	30 (27.1%)
Glycosylated hemoglobin(%), mean±SD	4.98±0.60
Fasting blood sugar (mg/dl), mean±SD	94.54±14.14
Hemoglobin (g/dl), mean±SD	7.81±2.82
Serum creatinine at enrollment (mg/dl), mean±SD	5.10±4.32
eGFR (ml/min/1.73 m ²) at enrollment, mean±SD	21.55±15.11
CKD stage 3	29 (26.5%)
CKD stage 4	37 (34.3%)
CKD stage 5	44 (39.2%)
Urine protein excretion (mg/day), mean±SD	701.0±294.6
Serum sodium (mmol/l), mean±SD	135.51±6.62
<120 mmol/l	3 (3%)
120–130 mmol/l	17 (15.6%)
130–135 mmol/l	21 (18.7%)
>135 mmol/l	70 (63.2%)
Serum potassium (mmol/L), mean±SD	5.13±4.28
<3.5 mmol/l	13 (12.0%)
3.5–5 mmol/l	74 (67.5%)
>5.5 mmol/l	23 (20.5%)
Serum uric acid (mg/dl), mean±SD	7.70±2.35
<7 mg/dl	40 (36.1%)
7–10 mg/dl	55 (50.0%)
>10 mg/dl	15 (13.9%)
Serum calcium (mg/dl), mean±SD	8.74±1.21
Serum phosphorous (mmol/l), mean±SD	4.70±1.87
Serum protein (g/dl), mean±SD	6.59±0.97
Serum albumin (g/dl), mean±SD	3.65±0.64
AST (U/l), mean±SD	31.48±35.91
ALT (U/l), mean±SD	26.24±31.22
Alkaline phosphate (U/l), mean±SD	147.96±106.61
ALT=alanine aminotransferase, AST=aspartate aminotransferase, BMI=body mass index, CKD=chronic kidney disease, CKDu=chronic kidney disease of unknown origin, eGFR=estimated glomerular filtration rate, SD=standard deviation	

At the time of presentation, the mean estimated glomerular filtration rate (eGFR) was 21.5 ± 15.1 ml/min/1.73m², indicating significantly reduced kidney function in the majority of patients. Among them, 26.5% had stage 3 chronic kidney disease (CKD), 34.3% had stage 4 CKD, and 39.2% had stage 5 CKD. This distribution reflects a high prevalence of advanced kidney disease in the population. Notably, 30% of the patients required renal replacement therapy, such as dialysis, underlining the severity of their renal impairment. A majority of the patients, 96.4%, presented with contracted kidneys, a sign of chronic kidney damage. Additionally, a significant proportion of the patients had electrolyte imbalances, with 36.7%

exhibiting hyponatremia (serum sodium <135 mmol/L), and 47.0% showing hyperuricemia (serum uric acid >7.7 mg/dL), both of which are commonly associated with kidney dysfunction. All patients tested negative for hepatitis B and hepatitis C, suggesting that viral hepatitis was not a contributing factor to their kidney disease. The mean urine protein excretion was 700.0 ± 294.6 mg/day, indicating the presence of proteinuria, a key marker of kidney damage [Table2]. A kidney biopsy was performed on six patients to further investigate the underlying pathology. The results revealed chronic interstitial nephritis and periglomerular fibrosis in all of them, with no evidence of immune deposition, suggesting that the

kidney damage was likely due to a non-immunologic, progressive fibrotic process rather

than an autoimmune disease [Figure 1].

Figure 1: Photomicrograph of renal biopsy male showing focal global glomerular sclerosis, mildly enlarged viable glomerulus with no proliferative activity, and focal chronic interstitial nephritis.

Discussion

Our study aims to shed light on the geographic distribution of Chronic Kidney Disease of unknown etiology (CKDu) in India, identifying new regions that bear a relatively high burden of the disease. This is a critical addition to the growing body of literature that suggests CKDu may be more widespread in rural India than has been previously acknowledged. The increasing prevalence of CKDu in regions traditionally considered low-risk raises concerns about its unnoticed impact on public health. One of the key findings is that the referral patterns from various parts of Gujarat indicate a notably higher prevalence in specific areas. These statistics highlight the geographic concentration of the disease in these regions, suggesting that factors such as environmental exposure, lifestyle, and agricultural practices may be contributing to the high burden of CKDu in these areas.

The elevated rates of CKDu in these districts suggest that there may be local environmental or occupational risk factors that require closer examination. It is essential to consider potential links to pesticide exposure, water contamination, and agricultural practices that are prevalent in rural areas, as these may contribute to kidney damage over time. Additionally, the lack of widespread awareness about CKDu in these regions may lead to delayed diagnoses and interventions, further

complicating the situation. Our findings underscore the importance of expanding CKDu research to encompass a broader geographic area, especially in rural regions, where healthcare access is often limited. These findings could serve as a foundation for future epidemiological studies and public health interventions that aim to mitigate the effects of CKDu in rural India [8].

Consistent with findings from global literature, most of the patients in our study presented with nonspecific symptoms and were diagnosed at a late stage of disease progression. This delay in diagnosis is a significant concern, as it means many patients require immediate kidney replacement therapies, such as dialysis or even kidney transplantation. The late presentation and the severity of the condition when diagnosed emphasize the need for greater awareness, early detection, and timely intervention to reduce the burden of Chronic Kidney Disease of unknown etiology (CKDu)[9,10].

In terms of potential contributing factors to CKDu, various environmental and occupational exposures have been hypothesized as important causes, with genetics playing a crucial role in predisposing individuals to the disease. Studies have suggested that genetic susceptibility, combined with environmental stressors, may be a key factor in the development of CKDu. However, despite these hypotheses, the precise etiology of CKDu remains largely un-

clear, and more research is needed to elucidate the underlying causes [11]. In our study, the majority of CKDu patients were farmers or laborers, occupations that involve strenuous physical labor and can place individuals at risk for repeated dehydration. Dehydration, particularly when frequent or prolonged, is considered a key risk factor for kidney damage, as it may lead to kidney injury over time. The hot and humid climate of the region further exacerbates the risk, as workers are more likely to experience dehydration due to excessive heat and physical exertion, without adequate opportunities for hydration.

Another important risk factor identified in our study is the widespread use of pesticides and fertilizers among farm workers, many of whom do so without using appropriate personal protective equipment (PPE). This chronic exposure to agricultural chemicals, including pesticides and fertilizers, is a significant concern, as these chemicals may contribute to kidney damage and increase the likelihood of developing CKDu. The use of PPE in agricultural settings is often limited due to cost, lack of awareness, and the difficulty of using such protective measures in the field. As a result, workers are regularly exposed to these harmful chemicals, which may contribute to the elevated rates of CKDu observed in farming communities [12]. Many of our patients also used over-the-counter analgesics and Ayurvedic and herbal medications to get relief from myalgia and back aches, which are common following strenuous physical activity required in agriculture and labor. These may have a role in the causation or progression of the disease.

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